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JIS

Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

Vision

“ENRICHING BEAUTIFUL MINDS TOWARDS INTELLIGENT MINDS”

The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) aims to disseminate scholarly research articles and papers to the wider community with the aim of offering an academic and scientific platform that provides an outlet to authors. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) is an open access online journal. Initially, the JIS will provide an online version, but is planning a print version later in this academic journey. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) focuses on a high-quality academic research articles and papers. All categories of research are of interest to the JIS, including insightful empirical studies, conceptual papers, commentary, essays, and theoretical articles.

JIS is an interdisciplinary platform and invites authors, academics, students, researchers, leaders, managers, scientists for their contributions in the disciplines of sciences, sociology, education, philosophy, humanities and management. Articles and Papers of scientific and academic rigour in Qualitative, Quantitative, Mixed or Blend methods are welcome.

JIS intends to publish two issues per annum (May and November).

Submissions to, and Publication in, the JIS is free.

All papers submitted for publication will be peer reviewed.

Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

mission is to “Guide Beautiful Minds towards Intellectual Enrichment”

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Editorial

Dear Readers,

We are pleased to announce the publication of our May 2026 issue.

In this Volume 10, Issue 1 of May 2026, research articles from different subject areas are covered and from authors of different countries. Articles published in the Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) will also be uploaded and archived in the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) and other scientific indexes for wider visibility and reachability.

To make it a broader interdisciplinary journal, JIS has accumulated articles from various multidisciplinary subjects with the intention of creating a one-platform gateway for all, providing easy access for readers worldwide.

Submission to JIS is open to authors from all disciplines. JIS has maintained a free, service-oriented academic platform for all since its founding, and the expenses are covered by the editor, which makes us feel that we are achieving our intended objectives towards a 'Felt-Positive need Motivation' (FPM) of 'Need for Serving' (NServe) and 'Need for continuation and contributing' (NCont/Cntrb).

We look forward to increased participation to help Enrich the Beautiful Minds toward Developing Intelligent Minds.

Thank you very much.

Let us join and collaborate together to **ENRICH the BEAUTIFUL MINDS
TOWARDS INTELLIGENT MINDS**

Mani Man Singh Rajbhandari. Ph.D.
Founder and Editor-in-Chief
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